

THE INFLUENCE OF TRAINING, ENVIRONMENT, AND MOTIVATION ON ARCHIVIST PERFORMANCE IN BULELENG REGENCY

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Abstract

Archiving is a crucial element in realizing accountable and transparent governance. However, internal archiving oversight of regional government agencies in Buleleng Regency indicates that some agencies have not yet achieved optimal performance, necessitating efforts to improve the performance of archivists. This study aims to analyze the influence of training, work environment, and motivation on the performance of archivists within regional government agencies in Buleleng Regency. This study uses a quantitative approach with multiple linear regression analysis method. The independent variables in this study are training (X₁), work environment (X₂), and motivation (X₃), while the dependent variable is the performance of archivists (Y). The study population is Government Employees with Work Agreements (PPPK) who serve as archivists in regional apparatus within the Buleleng Regency Government. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires using a Likert scale. The data obtained were analyzed through validity tests, reliability tests, classical assumption tests, and hypothesis testing using t-tests, F-tests, and coefficients of determination (R²). The results of the study indicate that training, work environment, and motivation simultaneously have a significant effect on the performance of archivists. Partially, training has no significant effect on performance, while work environment and motivation have a positive and significant effect. Motivation is the most dominant variable influencing performance. The coefficient of determination value of 0.734 indicates that 73.4% of the variation in archivist performance can be explained by these three variables, while the remainder is influenced by other factors outside the research model. These findings indicate that improving the performance of archivists needs to be focused on strengthening work motivation and improving a conducive work environment, accompanied by evaluating the effectiveness of training programs to make them more applicable and sustainable.

Keywords: performance, training, work environment, motivation, archiving.

INTRODUCTION

The implementation of archiving is one of the main pillars in realizing accountable, transparent, and responsive governance. In the modern public administration system, archives are no longer viewed merely as a collection of administrative documents, but rather as a strategic instrument that records the entire process of government administration. In Indonesia, this urgency is emphasized through Law Number 43 of 2009 concerning Archives, which mandates that every

state institution and regional government is required to organize archives in an orderly, systematic manner, and in accordance with national archival principles. Within this national framework, the National Archives of the Republic of Indonesia (ANRI) plays a central role as the institution responsible for fostering, developing, and supervising the implementation of archival records nationally to ensure the creation of authentic, reliable, complete, and trustworthy archives.

Conceptually, an archive is a record of information that has administrative, legal, financial, or historical value. The Liang Gie (2009) defines an archive as a collection of documents or documents stored systematically because they have utility value so they can be easily retrieved when needed. Sedarmayanti (2010) emphasizes that an archive is a document or record of information produced and received by an organization in carrying out its functions and activities. Basir Barthos (2013) views an archive as a written record, picture, or diagram that contains information about an event and serves to aid memory. Meanwhile, Sugiarto (2015) emphasizes that archives must be managed in a planned and orderly manner so that the retrieval process can be carried out quickly and accurately. From these various definitions, it can be concluded that an archive is an information asset with strategic value and must be managed through an archival process that includes creation, use, maintenance, depreciation, and preservation.

The success of archival management is determined not only by the existence of regulations, but also by the effectiveness of their implementation at the organizational level. To ensure compliance between archival practices and applicable standards, an archival oversight mechanism is required. Based on ANRI Regulation Number 6 of 2019 concerning Archival Supervision, archival oversight is the process of assessing the conformity of archival principles, rules, and standards with the practices implemented by archive creators and archival institutions. This oversight consists of external and internal oversight. External oversight is conducted on state institutions and local governments, while internal oversight is conducted within each archive creator's environment to assess the management of dynamic archives.

Within the Buleleng Regency Government, internal archival oversight is carried out by the Regional Archives and Library Service as the Regional Archival Institution. Internal audits are conducted on all regional apparatus by assessing two main aspects: the dynamic archives management aspect and the human resources aspect of archival matters. The dynamic archives management aspect covers the process of archive creation from the preparation of official documents, processing incoming and outgoing letters, filing, organizing active archives, managing inactive archives in the record center, archives services and access, and archives reduction. Meanwhile, the human resources aspect includes the competency of archivists and archives organizers, the responsibility for carrying out tasks, and the training received.

Data from the internal archival oversight of Buleleng Regency's regional government agencies during the 2023–2025 period shows that, despite a trend of improvement, several regional government agencies still received "sufficient" and "insufficient" ratings. In 2023, approximately 70% of regional government agencies received scores below 50. In 2024, this percentage decreased to 40%, and in 2025, it remained at 37.5%. This condition indicates that archival management is not yet fully optimal and requires continuous improvement efforts, particularly in the performance of archivists.

Performance in the context of public organizations can be understood as the level of achievement of individual or group work results in realizing organizational goals. Mathis and Jackson (2011) state that performance is behavior that demonstrates an individual's contribution to achieving organizational goals. Robbins and Judge (2013) emphasize that performance reflects measurable work results based on established standards. Mangkunegara (2004) also defines performance as the work results achieved by an individual in accordance with assigned responsibilities. In the context of archiving, the performance of archivists can be measured through adherence to archive management standards, the accuracy of filing procedures, the speed of archive retrieval, and the results of archiving supervision audits.

However, performance does not stand alone. Various organizational and individual factors influence it, including training, the work environment, leadership, and motivation. One important factor is human resource development through training. Dessler (2013) explains that training is a systematic process to improve employee knowledge, skills, and abilities so they can work more effectively. In the field of archiving, training is particularly important given the complexity of regulations and developments in information technology, including the implementation of the SRIKANDI application as a nationally integrated dynamic archival information system.

As the archival development institution, ANRI regularly holds various technical guidance and training programs, both in-person and online. In 2024, various training activities were implemented, including technical guidance on archives management, internal archival supervision workshops, technical assistance on correspondence in the SRIKANDI application, and technical guidance on archive reduction. However, most of the training was conducted online. This situation presents its own challenges because many archivists have other duties and cannot fully focus on participating in the training. As a result, the effectiveness of knowledge and skills transfer is less than optimal.

Another crucial issue is the limited human resources for archiving. Currently, there are only six functional archivists in Buleleng Regency, all of whom are located within the Regional Archives and Library Service. Other regional agencies do not yet have dedicated archivists, so archive management duties are often overlapped by other employees, including Government Employees with Work Agreements (PPPK).

The relatively frequent annual turnover of personnel leads to a lack of continuity in knowledge and experience in archives management. This situation has the potential to reduce the consistency and quality of archival management.

In addition to training and the availability of human resources, the work environment also plays a crucial role in supporting the performance of archivists. Nitisemito (1996) states that the work environment encompasses all conditions surrounding employees that can influence the performance of their duties. The work environment in archive management includes the availability of facilities such as folders, filing cabinets, partitions/guides, archive boxes, metal shelves, and adequate record center space. Without adequate facilities, the archive management process becomes inefficient and risks reducing the quality of archive management. In addition to physical aspects, the social and psychological environment—such as relationships between employees and leadership support—also influences work morale.

Motivation is an internal factor that is equally important in determining performance. High motivation will encourage archivists to work in a disciplined, meticulous, and proactive manner. Conversely, low motivation can result in work being done merely to fulfill administrative obligations without any effort to improve quality. Ekhsan (2018) emphasized that without motivation, employees will struggle to achieve optimal work standards. Therefore, organizations need to establish systems that not only provide training but also create a supportive work environment and reward good performance.

Previous studies have shown that archival issues in various regions are generally related to limited human resources, a lack of organizational commitment, an unsupportive work culture, and suboptimal follow-up on supervisory results. These findings reinforce the notion that improving the performance of archivists cannot be achieved in isolation but requires a comprehensive approach that simultaneously considers training, the work environment, and motivation.

Based on the above description, it can be concluded that although regulations and oversight mechanisms for archiving are in place, implementation challenges at the regional government level remain significant. Therefore, this study was conducted to analyze the influence of training, work environment, and motivation on the performance of archivists at regional government levels in Buleleng Regency. This research is expected to provide theoretical contributions to the development of human resource management studies in the public sector, while also providing practical recommendations for local governments in improving the quality of archiving management in a sustainable manner.

Theoretical review

2.1.1 Performance

1) Definition of Performance

Performance is a key concept in human resource management because it directly relates to the level of success of individuals and organizations in achieving predetermined goals. Hasan (2012) states that performance is the work results, both in quality and quantity, produced by an employee within a certain period according to their assigned responsibilities. Performance essentially reflects what employees do or do not do in carrying out their work, which impacts their contribution to the organization, including the quality of service provided.

According to Mangkunegara (2000:67), performance or work achievement is the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks according to their assigned responsibilities. This definition emphasizes the existence of objectively measurable results. Meanwhile, Wibowo (2007:67) views performance as a process of how work proceeds to achieve work results. This means that performance is not only seen from the final result, but also from the process of carrying out the work itself.

Hariman and Hilgert, in Zainur (2010:41), state that performance is the manifestation of the work of the apparatus, which is used as a basis for assessing whether or not the targets and objectives of a government organization have been achieved. Therefore, in the context of public organizations, performance is not only related to productivity but also to accountability and the achievement of public service targets.

Based on these various opinions, it can be concluded that employee performance is the work results achieved in carrying out job duties and responsibilities over a specific period, which can be used as a basis for assessing an individual's level of success or work achievement. Performance is an important indicator in assessing the extent to which an individual's contribution impacts the overall success of the organization.

In the context of this research, the performance referred to is the performance of archivists in the Buleleng Regency Regional Apparatus, which is reflected in the quality and quantity of archive management, accuracy of procedures, compliance with archiving standards, and the results of internal archiving supervision.

2) Performance Indicators

Performance indicators are used as measuring tools to assess the extent to which an employee is able to achieve expected work results. According to Robert and John (2006:378), performance indicators include:

1. **Quantity of results** , namely the amount of work that can be completed or achieved in a certain period.
2. **Quality of results** , namely the quality of work produced and the level of satisfaction with the results.
3. **Punctuality** , namely the suitability of work completion to the planned time.

4. **Attendance** , namely the level of employee attendance and discipline during working hours.
5. **The ability to work together** , namely the ability to work collaboratively in a team.

Meanwhile, Wibowo (2012) put forward more comprehensive performance indicators, namely:

1. **Goals** , namely the ideal conditions that you want to achieve in the future.
2. **Standards** , as a measure to determine whether the objectives have been achieved.
3. **Feedback** , as information regarding progress in achieving goals.
4. **Tools or means** , as supporting factors for work success.
5. **Competence** , namely the ability to carry out tasks.
6. **Motive** , namely the internal drive that drives individuals to work.
7. **Opportunity** , namely the opportunity given to demonstrate achievement.

In this study, the performance indicators of archivists refer to aspects of quantity, quality, timeliness, cooperation, and achievement of archive management standards according to applicable provisions.

3) Performance Measurement

Performance measurement is conducted to determine whether work implementation is in accordance with established plans and targets. Zeglat, in Lallatul et al. (2024), states that performance measurement is an important tool that enables organizations to achieve and control desired goals.

One widely used performance measurement method is **the Key Performance Indicator (KPI)** . According to Cascio (2016), KPIs are an effective method for assessing performance because they provide objective and measurable measures of individual achievement. KPIs serve not only as an evaluation tool but also as a guideline and motivator for achieving work targets.

From a learning and growth perspective, two important indicators in performance measurement are:

1. **Employee retention** , namely the organization's ability to retain potential employees.
2. **Employee satisfaction** , namely the level of comfort and satisfaction at work.

In the context of archiving, performance measurement can be seen from the results of archiving audits, the level of compliance with standards, and the effectiveness of dynamic archive management.

4) Factors Affecting Performance

According to Robbins (2015), factors that influence performance include:

1. Motivation , as an encouragement to carry out work activities.
2. Workload , namely the demands of tasks that must be completed.
3. Job characteristics , including the content and conditions of the job.

4. Work discipline , namely compliance with rules and responsibilities.

In this study, the factors studied specifically are training, work environment, and motivation as variables that influence the performance of archivists.

2.1.2 Training

1) Definition of Training

Training is a systematic process designed to improve an individual's ability to perform their job more effectively. Gilley and Maycunich (2000) state that training aims to improve the skills, knowledge, and abilities of individuals or groups within an organization.

According to Kasmir (2016), good training will improve employee performance. Gomes (2003:197) defines training as an effort to improve employee performance in specific jobs for which they are responsible. Hanggraeni (2012) emphasizes that the goal of training is to improve skills and work quality, which in turn improves performance.

In the context of archiving, training is crucial because managing records requires specialized competencies, an understanding of regulations, and technical skills in using archival information systems like SRIKANDI. Without adequate training, archivists will struggle to keep up with technological developments and national archival standards.

2) Training Methods

According to Mangkunegara (2016), training methods consist of:

1. On the job training
2. Demonstration method
3. Classroom training (off the job training)

Sedarmayanti (2013) explains that on-the-job training allows employees to learn directly through practice, while off-the-job training is more theoretical and allows participants to focus without the distraction of routine work.

3) Training Indicators

Mangkunegara (2016) stated that training indicators include:

1. Instructor
2. Participant
3. Material
4. Method
5. Training objectives
6. Target

Wahyuningsih (2019) also added the importance of clarity of objectives, relevance of material, participatory methods, and qualifications of trainers and participants.

4) Factors Influencing Training

According to Kasmir (2019), factors that influence the success of training include:

1. Training participants
2. Instructor
3. Training materials

4. Training location
5. Training environment
6. Training time

2.1.3 Work Environment

1) Understanding the Work Environment

The work environment is everything around employees that can influence the performance of their duties. Nitisemito, in Hertanto (2011:5), states that the work environment encompasses all conditions surrounding employees that can influence their work. George R. Terry (2006:23) emphasizes that the work environment is the forces that directly and indirectly influence organizational performance.

A positive work environment creates a sense of comfort, safety, and conduciveness, enabling employees to perform optimally. Conversely, an unsupportive environment can decrease productivity and morale.

2) Work Environment Indicators

According to Nitisemito (2020), work environment indicators include:

1. **Working atmosphere**
2. **Relationships with coworkers**
3. **Availability of work facilities or equipment**

In the context of archiving, facilities such as archive shelves, filing cabinets, archive boxes, and adequate record center space are important indicators.

2.1.4 Motivation

1) Understanding Motivation

Motivation is the drive that causes someone to take action to achieve a specific goal. Hasibuan (2017) states that motivation is a factor that causes and encourages someone to work hard to achieve optimal results. Samsudin (2015) defines motivation as the process of encouraging someone to carry out a specific goal.

In the context of archivists, motivation can be built through leadership support, recognition of performance, opportunities for self-development, and clarity of roles within the organization.

2) Motivation Indicators

According to Hasibuan (2019) based on Herzberg's theory, motivation indicators include:

1. Achievement
2. Recognition
3. The work itself
4. Responsibility
5. Advancement
6. Potential development

3) Factors that Influence Motivation

According to Ardana (2008), motivational factors consist of:

1. **Individual characteristic factors** (interests, attitudes, needs, abilities, knowledge, emotions, values).
2. **Job factors** (salary, supervision, working conditions, organizational culture, responsibility, opportunities for development).

2.2 Relevant Research Review

Previous research serves as a foundation to strengthen the theoretical arguments and demonstrate the position of this study. Various previous studies have shown that training, work environment, motivation, work discipline, and communication have a positive and significant influence on employee performance, both partially and simultaneously.

The difference between this research and previous research lies in:

1. **The research location** was carried out at the Buleleng Regency Regional Apparatus.
2. **The research period** is 2025.
3. **The research variables**, namely using three independent variables (training, work environment, motivation) and one dependent variable (archivist performance).

Thus, this research has novelty in the context of location, time, and combination of variables studied, especially in the field of regional government archives.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research method uses a quantitative approach with the aim of testing hypotheses regarding the influence of training, work environment, and motivation on the performance of archivists. Quantitative research was chosen because it is able to explain the relationship between variables in a measurable manner through statistical analysis. The independent variables in this study are training (X_1), work environment (X_2), and motivation (X_3), while the dependent variable is the performance of archivists (Y). Data obtained from respondents were processed and analyzed to determine the magnitude of the influence of each variable, both partially and simultaneously.

The research was conducted at the Buleleng Regency Regional Archives and Library Service, with the research subjects being Government Employees with Work Agreements (PPPK) assigned as archive organizers in regional apparatus within the Buleleng Regency Government. The research implementation period lasted for approximately five months. The research population was all PPPK who carry out duties as archive organizers, while the sampling technique used purposive sampling with the criteria for respondents being PPPK who actively serve as archive organizers.

Data collection was conducted through the distribution of closed-ended questionnaires compiled based on the indicators of each research variable and

supported by documentation techniques. The research instrument used a Likert scale with a score range of 1 to 5, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Performance variables were measured through indicators of quantity of results, quality of results, timeliness, and attendance. Training variables were measured through indicators of instructors, participants, materials, methods, training objectives, and targets. Work environment variables were measured through work atmosphere, relationships with coworkers, and availability of facilities. Meanwhile, motivation variables were measured through indicators of achievement, recognition, the work itself, responsibility, progress, and development of individual potential.

Prior to data analysis, the research instruments were first tested for validity and reliability. Validity testing was conducted to ensure that each question item adequately measures the intended variable. Reliability testing was performed using Cronbach's Alpha, with a value greater than 0.70 considered reliable. Furthermore, classical assumption tests, including normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests, were conducted to ensure the regression model met statistical requirements.

The data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis with the equation model $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$. This analysis aims to determine the direction and magnitude of the influence of training variables, work environment, and motivation on the performance of archivists. Hypothesis testing is carried out through the t test to determine the partial effect, the F test to determine the simultaneous effect, and the coefficient of determination (R^2) test to determine how much the independent variables contribute in explaining the dependent variable. With this method, it is hoped that an empirical picture will be obtained regarding the factors that influence the performance of archivists in regional apparatuses in Buleleng Regency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Research Results

4.1.1 General Description and Research Object

The Buleleng Regency Regional Archives and Library Service has a long institutional history. It was first established in Singaraja in 1959 under the name Bali Provincial State Library. Along with the development of national policies in the field of libraries and archives, there have been several changes in the nomenclature and institutional structure. Based on Decree of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 095/0/1979, this institution was transformed into a Regional Library under the Ministry of Education and Culture. Subsequently, based on Presidential Decree Number 4 of 1989 concerning the National Library, the institution's name was changed to the Bali Regional Library.

With the implementation of regional autonomy policies through the Law on Regional Government and Buleleng Regency Regulation Number 2 of 2001, the status of this institution is no longer a vertical institution, but rather part of the regional apparatus. Through Buleleng Regency Regulation Number 4 of 2008 and Regent Regulation Number 61 of 2008, it was designated as the Buleleng Regency Library and Archives Office. Then in 2017, based on Buleleng Regent Regulation Number 75 of 2016, the nomenclature was again adjusted to the Buleleng Regency Archives and Library Service.

Structurally, this service has three main areas: the Development, Management, and Supervision of Archives; the Library Development and Reading Culture Sector; and the Library Processing, Services, and Preservation Sector. In carrying out its duties, the service runs various programs, including the Regional Government Affairs Support Program, the Library Development Program, the National Collection and Ancient Manuscripts Preservation Program, and the Dynamic and Static Archives Management Program.

To ensure the quality of archival management, internal oversight was conducted through archival audits of 40 regional government agencies within the Buleleng Regency Government. This activity was facilitated by the Regional Archives and Library Service and implemented by an Internal Archival Supervisory Team established by the Regent. This research focused on Government Employees with Work Agreements (PPPK) who served as archival administrators within these regional agencies.

4.1.2 Research Prerequisite Test

Before the analysis was conducted, the validity and reliability of the research instrument were tested on 30 initial respondents using SPSS version 25. The test results showed that all statement items had a Corrected Item Total Correlation value greater than r table (0.361), so that all indicators were declared valid. The Cronbach's Alpha value for all variables was above 0.70, so the instrument was declared reliable and suitable for use in research.

Next, a classical assumption test was performed. The results of the normality test using a P-P plot graph showed that the residual points spread along a diagonal line, thus concluding that the data were normally distributed. The multicollinearity test showed that all variables had a Tolerance value > 0.10 and a VIF < 10 , thus preventing multicollinearity. The heteroscedasticity test using a scatterplot showed no specific pattern and the points were randomly distributed, thus the model met the assumption of homoscedasticity.

By fulfilling all prerequisite tests, the regression model is declared suitable for further analysis.

4.1.3 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The results of multiple linear regression analysis produce the following equation:

$$Y = 1.111 + 0.080X_1 + 0.265X_2 + 0.406X_3$$

This equation shows that simultaneously Training (X_1), Work Environment (X_2), and Motivation (X_3) have an influence on the Performance of Archivists (Y).

Partially, the Training variable has a significance value of 0.149 (>0.05) so it does not significantly influence performance. The Work Environment variable has a significance value of 0.002 (<0.05) so it has a positive and significant effect. The Motivation variable has a significance value of 0.000 (<0.05) so it has a positive and significant effect and is the most dominant variable based on the highest Beta value (0.579).

The results of the simultaneous test (F test) showed a calculated F value of 127.230 with a significance of 0.000 (<0.05), so that the three variables together had a significant effect on performance.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.734 shows that 73.4% of performance variation can be explained by Training, Work Environment, and Motivation, while 26.6% is influenced by other factors outside the research model.

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1 The Effect of Training on the Performance of Archivists

The research results showed that training had no significant impact on the performance of archivists. This indicates that the training provided was not fully capable of significantly improving the quantity, quality, punctuality, or attendance of work.

This insignificance could be due to several factors, such as training materials that aren't fully relevant to actual job needs, ineffective training methods, or a lack of post-training follow-up. Furthermore, work experience and long-established routine work habits among PPPK are likely more dominant than the impact of formal training.

These findings indicate that training alone is not enough to improve performance if it is not supported by motivation and a conducive work environment.

4.2.2 The Influence of the Work Environment on the Performance of Archivists

The work environment has been shown to have a positive and significant impact on performance. This suggests that a comfortable work environment, harmonious relationships between employees, and the availability of adequate work facilities can improve the productivity and quality of work of archivists.

A positive work environment can improve concentration, reduce stress, and encourage more effective teamwork. Therefore, environmental factors are a key determinant of performance improvement, particularly in archival work that requires precision and administrative order.

4.2.3 The Influence of Motivation on the Performance of Archivists

Motivation is the most dominant variable influencing performance. The higher the work motivation, the higher the archivist's performance. Motivation encourages employees to be more disciplined, responsible, and results-oriented.

Intrinsic motivation, such as a sense of responsibility and job satisfaction, and extrinsic motivation, such as rewards and recognition, have been shown to be key factors in increasing productivity. This confirms that internal employee motivation plays a strategic role in improving organizational performance.

4.2.4 The Simultaneous Effect of Training, Work Environment, and Motivation

Simultaneously, all three variables significantly influenced performance. This indicates that archivist performance is not determined by a single factor, but rather by a combination of competence, working conditions, and the individual's internal drive. Although training is not partially significant, when combined with motivation and the work environment, it still contributes to the performance model. Motivation acts as the primary driver, while the work environment provides external support for optimizing performance.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of archiving is a strategic element in realizing accountable, transparent, and responsive governance as mandated by Law Number 43 of 2009 concerning Archives. In the context of the Buleleng Regency Government, internal archiving supervision carried out by the Regional Archives and Library Service shows improvement from year to year, but there are still a number of regional agencies that have not reached the optimal category. This condition indicates that improving the quality of archiving management, particularly in the aspect of the performance of archivists, remains an urgent need.

Based on the results of research conducted using a quantitative approach using multiple linear regression analysis, it can be concluded that training, work environment, and motivation simultaneously have a significant influence on the performance of archivists in regional government agencies in Buleleng Regency. This indicates that performance improvement cannot be achieved partially, but rather through an integrated approach that takes into account competency factors, working conditions, and internal employee motivation.

Partially, the training variable did not show a significant impact on the performance of archivists. This finding indicates that the training provided so far has not been fully effective in improving the quality and quantity of work. Factors such as the predominantly online training method, limited participant focus due to multiple tasks, and a lack of post-training follow-up are suspected to be contributing to the suboptimal impact of training on performance.

Conversely, the work environment has been shown to have a positive and significant impact on the performance of archivists. The availability of adequate archival facilities, a conducive work environment, and harmonious working relationships are important supporting factors in increasing the effectiveness and accuracy of archives management. In jobs that require administrative order and procedural accuracy, such as archiving, a supportive work environment is a crucial factor.

Motivation is the most dominant variable influencing the performance of archivists. The higher the work motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, the higher the level of performance achieved. Motivation encourages employees to work with greater discipline, responsibility, and results-oriented. These findings confirm that psychological factors and internal motivation play a strategic role in improving individual performance in the public sector.

The high coefficient of determination indicates that most of the variation in archivist performance can be explained by the combination of these three variables. Therefore, efforts to improve the quality of archiving management in Buleleng Regency need to focus on strengthening employee motivation, improving the work environment, and evaluating and refining the training system to make it more applicable and sustainable.

Overall, this research provides theoretical contributions in the development of human resource management studies in the public sector, particularly in the field of local government archives, and provides practical recommendations for local governments in designing strategies to improve the performance of archivists in a comprehensive and sustainable manner.

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